

INVESTIGATING THERMAL PERFORMANCE OF TRADITIONAL MUD HOUSES IN KHULNA: A COMPARATIVE ANALYSIS USING ECOTECH SOFTWARE

A. Rahman¹, P.S. Anik², M.S.R. Shovon³

^{1,2,3}B.Arch. Student, Department of architecture, KUET, Khulna, Bangladesh, e-mail: rahman1725007@stud.kuet.ac.bd

Abstract

The temperature of the world has increased in recent years and due to this rising heat, the climatic condition has drastically changed. As a result, the indoor temperature of our habitable houses has increased and the energy consumption is very high which makes eco-friendly building development a very important issue.

Building material is involved directly and indirectly with the change of this built environment as every individual material has different properties and they react differently to climatic conditions. As a deltaic country, Bangladesh is blessed with numerous natural resources, such as mud, bamboo and etc. Traditionally, mud is used as the core construction material for building structures. Mud being a really cheap, available, and environmentally friendly building fabric, is used extensively for building development within the country. Mud encompasses an extraordinary capacity of containing heat and low thermal conductivity which moves forward the warm soundness interior of the building compared to other building materials.

This paper focuses to find an alternative material to ensure a better thermal performance of the built environment. To do this, 4-5 houses made from mud will be selected as case study and comparative analysis of hourly temperature profile, monthly heating/cooling loads and Resource consumption inside buildings will be done using ECOTECH software simulation. The resultant information from thermal simulation will analyze, compare and discuss the thermal behavior, comfort and energy consumption of mud houses. This research will contribute to suggest an alternative thermally comfortable, low-cost building materials instead of dried brick and advancement of passive and low energy architecture towards a sustainable future.

Keywords

Mud house, Thermal performance, Energy consumption, Thermal comfort.

1. Introduction

Prior to the industrial revolution and the development of mechanical heating and cooling, bioclimatic methods were the only ones available for creating somewhat acceptable temperatures inside of structures. Active heating and cooling systems exist today to guarantee interior comfort, although major energy inputs are needed. However, with a greater fuel economy and a dual challenge of crisis and global warming worries, the extent of thermal comfort levels, which will require energy that will become unfavorable to environmental sustainability, Architecture that can adapt to changing climates gives answers to these difficulties. Publications state that traditional and indigenous environmentally conscious cultures start in the home. Lessons from traditional and vernacular architecture design strategy of buildings can achieve benefit for future development.[1]

The traditional houses of Bangladesh are seen to be an excellent example of warm, humid, tropical houses that are adapted to local climates and well-integrated with local customs and materials. The traditional houses in Bangladesh are less warm during the day, but they rapidly become pleasant after dusk, according to user experience. Even though these conventional construction materials are quite sustainable, people are still looking for more robust materials like bricks, concrete, and corrugated iron sheets. The government or non-government organizations, as well as mosques and temples, all have structures built of brick or concrete, including the top members of the town. The typical earth, bamboo, or mud dwelling seems to have nothing in common with the so-called ideal houses.[2]

Bangladeshi vernacular architecture is a product of the notion of living in harmony with nature. Mud houses are seen mostly in all over Bangladesh as traditional dwelling. It is also a popular traditional house in the southern region, like Khulna. A mud house is constructed with a mixture of mud, clay, sand, water, and binding materials

like rice husks or straw. Due to its abundance, low cost, and strength, it was utilized by the majority of ancient civilizations.[3]

There are many classic examples of the traditional mud houses in Khulna which has sustained through ages. The walls of the houses are generally made of thick mud or ‘Kancha it’ (sun dried brick). The finishing material of this sundried brick houses was clay and mud mortar were used to bind the bricks. The roofs were basically made of thatch or ‘Golpata’. But in recent extent, C.I. sheets are used as roofing material as water cannot penetrate the surface and thus makes it more sustainable. The rural settlement’s form and structure of Khulna are the outcome of centuries of adaptation and learning, which displays a variety of different physical and social factors such as climate, economy, socio-cultural values, geology and technological factors. It is an intensely knit structure of small residential groups made of thatch roofs, small openings and thick mud walls. Maximum house layouts remain same in term of size, shape, function and detailing.

	January	February	March	April	May	June	July	August	September	October	November	December
Avg. Temperature °C	18.9 °C	22.4 °C	26.6 °C	29.1 °C	29.5 °C	28.8 °C	27.8 °C	27.8 °C	27.5 °C	26.3 °C	23.2 °C	20 °C
(°F)	(66) °F	(72.2) °F	(79.9) °F	(84.4) °F	(85) °F	(83.8) °F	(82.1) °F	(82) °F	(81.4) °F	(79.3) °F	(73.8) °F	(68) °F
Min. Temperature °C (°F)	12.9 °C (55.3) °F	16.2 °C (61.1) °F	21 °C (69.7) °F	24.9 °C (76.8) °F	26.2 °C (79.1) °F	26.5 °C (79.6) °F	25.9 °C (78.5) °F	25.7 °C (78.2) °F	25.2 °C (77.3) °F	23 °C (73.4) °F	18.4 °C (65.1) °F	14.5 °C (58.2) °F
Max. Temperature °C	25.1 °C	28.5 °C	32.5 °C	34.3 °C	33.6 °C	32 °C	30.7 °C	30.8 °C	30.7 °C	30.1 °C	28.4 °C	25.7 °C
(°F)	(77.1) °F	(83.3) °F	(90.6) °F	(93.8) °F	(92.6) °F	(89.7) °F	(87.3) °F	(87.4) °F	(87.2) °F	(86.2) °F	(83) °F	(78.3) °F
Precipitation / Rainfall	8	20	47	113	196	319	360	301	243	143	40	11
mm (in)	(0)	(0)	(1)	(4)	(7)	(12)	(14)	(11)	(9)	(5)	(1)	(0)
Humidity(%)	65%	61%	61%	71%	78%	84%	86%	86%	87%	83%	71%	67%
Rainy days (d)	1	2	4	8	12	17	21	21	19	11	2	1
avg. Sun hours (hours)	9.0	9.3	9.4	8.8	8.2	7.9	7.6	7.7	7.8	8.3	8.7	8.6

Figure 1. Yearly Climate Data of Khulna [5]

2. Materials and Methods

Related published documents and researches has conducted research on the thermal performance, thermal mass of buildings and the advantages of mud houses in hot dry climate and thermal comfort of mud houses In Bangladesh.

Hiroshi, in his research study in Japan, researched traditional firm houses using in situ measurement and software simulation. Datta and Mustafa used ‘ECOTECT’ simulation software and in-situ measurement technique using data loggers to find the result of hourly temperature and inter-zonal heat gain.

This study uses only software simulation method to find the result of thermal comfort and energy consumption. This simulation was performed using ‘ECOTECT’ and the values of different factors such as occupancy number, hours of operation, HVAC system were putted manually. Mainly hourly temperature, monthly heating/cooling loads and Resource consumption were analyzed by the simulation software. It should be noted that the weather data file of Jessore was used to compensate the simulation as the climate of Khulna and Jessore are quite similar. The wall thickness was 300 mm and the wall were made of fully mud. For roofing corrugated galvanized sheets are used and the dimension of the house is 15 ft by 30 ft. The comfort band is selected between 18-26°C.

Figure 2. Methodology Process (Performed by author)

3. Results and Discussions

March, September and December were selected months for the simulation. The analysis of the mud house is given below:

Figure 3. Simulated Mud wall house in ECOTECT (Performed by author)

Figure 4. Surveyed Mud walled houses in Khulna (clicked by author)

Most of the mud houses are made of sun-dried bricks and rammed earth. Sun-dried bricks are constructed using mud mortar. In past, thatch was mainly used as roofing material but nowadays Corrugated Galvanized Iron sheets are being used. Nearly each house has verandah in the front, which are mainly used for semi outdoor interactive space and a buffer zone.

Figure 5. Surveyed Mud walled houses in Khulna (clicked by author)

Figure 6. Plan of a typical Mud house (sketched by author)

Figure 7. Mud wall (sketched by author)

The house is elevated 1.5 ft from the ground. There is a six feet tall door in each room. The windows are quite smaller than usual, they have basically 2 ft height and 4 ft width. The sill height is 4 ft from the plinth level. The pitch roof is constructed by vertical timber post.

Figure 8. Section of a typical Mud house (sketched by author)

3.1. Hourly Temperature Profile

The hourly temperature profile indicates that the indoor temperature of the mud house remains nearly the same all day long. The temperature fluctuation is not that much inside of a mud walled house which ensures comfort of the dwellers. There are three shaded zones and two lines in the graph. The blue shaded zone indicates the cold zone, the red shaded zone indicates the warm zone and the white shaded zone indicates the comfort band. The blue line represents the outdoor temperature and the bold red line represents the indoor temperature of a room.

HOURLY TEMPERATURES - 1 Hour	INSIDE (C)	OUTSIDE (C)	TEMP.DIF (C)
00	26.0	22.3	3.7
01	25.6	21.6	4.0
02	25.1	21.0	4.1
03	24.7	20.3	4.4
04	24.5	19.9	4.6
05	24.4	19.5	4.9
06	24.6	20.9	3.7
07	25.0	22.3	2.7
08	25.7	23.7	2.0
09	26.6	25.2	1.4
10	27.7	26.6	1.1
11	28.7	28.0	0.7
12	28.2	27.9	0.3
13	28.7	27.9	0.8
14	28.2	27.8	0.4
15	28.0	27.7	0.3
16	26.6	27.7	-1.1
17	26.4	27.6	-1.2
18	26.1	26.6	-0.5
19	26.0	25.6	0.4
20	25.9	24.5	1.4
21	25.8	23.5	2.3
22	25.6	22.5	3.1
23	25.3	21.5	3.8

Figure 9. Hourly temperature graph for 1st March (Performed by author)

This graph shows that the Indoor temperature remains in the comfort band (24.4-28.7°C) for a whole day except for 5 hours and the temperature fluctuation is very small. Which ensures the thermal comfort of the occupants. The outdoor temperature is more fluctuating than the indoor temperature and it touches the warm zone slightly.

HOURLY TEMPERATURES - 1 Hour	INSIDE (C)	OUTSIDE (C)	TEMP.DIF (C)
00	26.0	26.4	-0.4
01	28.1	26.3	1.8
02	28.1	26.1	2.0
03	27.9	26.0	1.9
04	27.8	26.2	1.6
05	27.8	26.3	1.5
06	28.0	26.8	1.2
07	28.4	27.4	1.0
08	28.2	27.9	0.3
09	29.7	28.5	1.2
10	29.1	29.1	0.0
11	29.1	29.7	-0.6
12	29.7	30.6	-0.9
13	31.1	31.4	-0.3
14	31.3	31.3	-0.0
15	29.8	30.6	-0.8
16	28.6	29.0	-0.4
17	28.1	27.3	0.8
18	28.0	27.2	0.8
19	28.0	27.0	1.0
20	28.1	26.9	1.2
21	28.1	27.0	1.1
22	28.4	27.0	1.4
23	28.2	27.1	1.1

Figure 10. Hourly temperature graph for 1st September (Performed by author)

In September, both the outdoor and indoor temperature touches the warm zone (26-31.3°C) that means the climate is little bit hot and the indoor comfort is slightly less than that of March. But still the maximum outdoor temperature is more than the maximum indoor temperature, because of the building material.

HOURLY TEMPERATURES - 1 Hour	INSIDE (C)	OUTSIDE (C)	TEMP.DIF (C)
00	21.7	16.8	4.9
01	21.2	16.0	5.2
02	20.5	15.3	5.2
03	20.0	14.5	5.5
04	19.9	14.1	5.8
05	19.7	13.7	6.0
06	20.0	15.1	4.9
07	20.4	16.5	3.9
08	20.9	17.9	3.0
09	22.0	20.4	1.6
10	23.3	22.8	0.5
11	24.4	25.3	-0.9
12	24.7	25.6	-0.9
13	24.8	25.8	-1.0
14	24.3	26.1	-1.8
15	23.7	24.8	-1.1
16	22.3	23.4	-1.1
17	21.8	22.1	-0.3
18	21.5	20.6	0.9
19	21.2	19.0	2.2
20	21.0	17.5	3.5
21	21.1	17.1	4.0
22	21.1	16.6	4.5
23	21.0	16.2	4.8

Figure 11. Hourly temperature graph for 1st December (Performed by author)

The graph of December is showing that the indoor temperature of mud house remains in the comfort band for the whole day where the outdoor temperature touches the cold zone and it fluctuates throughout the whole day. Thus mud house in winter season is more comfortable and warm for the occupants and it remains nearly the same for the whole day.

3.2. Monthly heating / cooling loads

The heating or cooling load means the energy consumption or electricity consumption of a house in a month to obtain thermal comfortability using active cooling or heating method. This can be anything like boiler, air conditioner, fan etc. The houses that we surveyed mostly use ceiling fans for their active cooling method. In the simulation software we used only cooling method in HVAC system, because these houses use only fan in summer season.

MONTHLY HEATING/COOLING LOADS

All Visible Thermal Zones

Comfort: Zonal Bands

Max Heating: 0.0 C - No Heating.

Max Cooling: 3413 W at 00:00 on 22nd May

MONTH	HEATING (Wh)	COOLING (Wh)	TOTAL (Wh)
Jan	0	0	0
Feb	0	0	0
Mar	0	33081	33081
Apr	0	61585	61585
May	0	65263	65263
Jun	0	61685	61685
Jul	0	60651	60651
Aug	0	61901	61901
Sep	0	54154	54154
Oct	0	49089	49089
Nov	0	13624	13624
Dec	0	0	0
TOTAL	0	461034	461034
PER M²	0	11384	11384
Floor Area:		40.500 m²	

Figure 12. Monthly heating or cooling loads (Performed by author)

It shows that the total energy consumed over a year for cooling purpose is 461034 Wh or 461 Kwh. So, the total cost for this energy using only fan for the whole year is 2636 taka. (TK 5.72 per unit for 76 - 200-unit consumer) [4]

4. Conclusion

Indigenous architectural style of our country gives us more efficient and sustainable solution to many problems with least negative impacts on the environment. The principles of this traditional architectural style can also be applied in modern era. The research on mud houses confirmed that using thatch and mud for the construction kept the interior of the hut cooler in summer season. Through a process known as passive solar heating, mud absorbs sunlight and gradually heats the building throughout the day. This keeps the interior of the structure cozy in the winter and cool in the summer. Using resources that are close to construction site have certain benefits for using construction materials for instance. The material from the same climate environments exhibits more flexibility and has a longer life time and better economic. From environmental perspective, this as having additional benefits like: a) low environmental effect of manufacturing, renewability, and even natural disintegration (b) a substantial

decrease in processing and transportation-related energy. However, with suitable design considerations including optimal construction orientation, increasing the proportion of openings, and enhancing the built environment, the cooling impact of these indigenous mud houses may be further enhanced, as can the living conditions within the huts. Unlike conventional homes, which are typically made with synthetic or industrial material, mud huts are typically created nearly entirely from natural and clean resources. In order to revitalize the environment, tradition, and culture, mud buildings should be used more frequently as they are eco-friendly.

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